

THE SCHOOL GUIDE TO FAMILY-BASED OPEN SCIENCE SCHOOLING

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In Collaboration with the Project Partners and School Teams

Family-based Open Science Schooling Project (OSS)

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About This Electronic Guidebook

This guidebook is an interactive e-book with various elements that you can interact with. It includes text, pictures, links and videos. We hope this electronic guidebook gives you a more engaging experience while reading through.

The [blue texts](#) in the paragraphs consist of hyperlinks. Click the links to visit the web pages.

All pictures in this electronic guidebook have interactive features. Click the pictures to follow a hyperlink, to enlarge, to watch the video or to just make them wiggle.

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Executive Summary

In Europe, Family-based Open Science Schooling (FBOSS) is still at the basic level since it is not sufficiently grounded in common teaching-learning school practices and because it is unusual to involve parents in students' learning process at school. Yet, the open science schooling innovative pedagogical approach to science education has highlighted the significant role family members can play in fostering students' motivation in science learning. What is more, the approach has pointed out that the engagement of students in real-life experimentations alongside their families and undertaken with the local community contributes to their learning process in various fields of science including physics, chemistry, social science, environmental science, etc.

To further the implementation of Family-based Open Science Schooling and contribute to students' learning experiences in various fields of science, this interactive e-book offers a two-fold guide pack:

1. **C**apacity building for schools and science teachers on the implementation of science learning activities developed alongside students with the active involvement of their families. This capacity building material is based on state-of-the-art reported outcomes and the practical experiences gained by the knowledge and practice partners who jointly implemented the Erasmus+ Family-based Open Science Schooling project in Finland, Portugal, Bulgaria, Poland, Greece, Turkey, and Lithuania in 2020-2022.
2. **G**uidance to motivate family members to engage in their children's science learning and how to support them at home.

Motivating Families to Get Involved – Useful Teachers’ Strategies

“be positive and smile”

“Establish rapport. We need to know and trust one another. If teachers are not held in respect, they is no way parents will join school activities, especially in science.”

“Make F2F meetings, individual meetings, personal phone calls helped to make communication regular.”

“Having F2F meetings with families and telling them clearly and understandable about project mission.”

“Just asking parents to help kids and not giving them enough information did not work.”

“The results show that most people faced internet problems and did not have the knowledge to use and solve problems related to technology. So, we need to educate parents how to use technologies.”

“Instead of talking at families, first listen to families.”

“We tried to explain to them that it would be great for them to spent some time with their children and be the good example for the students and work with the missions.”

“Instead of giving families expert advice about what to do, encourage families to experiment with new practices.”

Parents' Perspective on Their Participation in Family-based Open Science Schooling

Based on the data collected, families had a positive opinion about Family-based Open Science Schooling and thought the project helped both their own and their children in many different regards.

Participation in Family-based
Open Science Schooling

“Before she was “a fan” of Literature, she could write stories and essays, but now with this project her interest in Chemistry also emerged. She started searching different experiments and she started jumping in home like a kid asking which experiment she could do first.”

“Me and my child have always got along, and to say that this project has helped us grow as a familial entity would be an understatement. We're closer than ever before, and now my child even insists on going on trips or doing experiments together.”

“It is very pleasant when in the evening, after dinner all of us decide to make an experiment, rather than watching a movie or television.”

“On my own, it's not much easy, because there's no foundation to start from, and besides, I can't always be able to tell what my child wants in their education. OSS seems to mitigate this problem somewhat, which I'm happy for, because that eases my own.”

Students' Perspectives on the Role of Their Families

Students' feedback also highlights the significant role their parents played during the Family-based Open Science Schooling project. The model was originally created by the participating Bulgarian students. During the last Mobility event in March 2022, it got revised and refined by all participating students from five countries.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

What is Family-based Open Science Schooling?

Based on state-of-the-art research, Family-based Open Science Schooling practice focuses on deeply involving students through co-creation practices in the elaboration and implementation of discovery science missions to propose solutions to problems which students encounter in their everyday life. Through its co-creational design, Family-based Open Science Schooling allows for a significant role of families in the science learning process of their children. What is more, through co-creation, students are no longer mere recipients of information and spectators of activities. Instead, they are active creators in the development of their learning projects and the advancement of the project as a whole since the realization of discovery science missions is driven by students and their families and not by science teachers. Students and their families decide how and which science missions they want to realize that are related to their everyday life and local community.

INTRODUCTION

Parent: *“The project definitely helped us become closer. We got closer and gained more authority as knowledgeable parents.”*

Student: *“Well, the goods of this situation were that me and my father got closer and some fun and enjoyed it, we both learned a lot of things during the process. Since it was our first time doing this.”*

What is Family-based Open Science Schooling?

Family-based Open Science Schooling (FBOSS) practice offers students and their families the following inventive science experiences through discovery science missions:

- ▶ **A**longside their families, students carry out science missions that contribute to the well-being of their local community and in cooperation with local stakeholders and science resources.
- ▶ **T**he implementation of the science missions entails creativity, pioneering, detective work, social interactions, and storytelling.
- ▶ **T**he science missions encourage students to develop their own approach and techniques to tackle the everyday issue under study rather than those stipulated by the educational system.
- ▶ **T**he science missions invite students to follow their own interests and to engage in meaningful activities in cooperation with local stakeholders and science resources and alongside their families.
- ▶ **T**he science missions allow students to link their science learning process to their everyday life at home and to gain the support of their parents.
- ▶ **F**amily-based Open Science Schooling promotes students' documentation of their thoughts and feelings as well as reflections about their selected mission's development.

Participatory Approach to Family-based Open Science Schooling

Family-based Open Science Schooling practice is anchored in the participatory design approach to Open Science Schooling. It seeks to actively involve all stakeholders in the design process of the discovery science mission to ensure that the result meets the needs of students, their families, and local communities and is usable. In the context of Family-based Open Science Schooling, participatory design means that students and their families take part in the project decision-making stage, project implementation, as well as the project outcomes alongside teachers, local community members, and researchers. This approach summarizes the co-creation methodology of the Family-based Open Science Schooling practice – all project stakeholders work together to create authentic science learning experiences that foster deeper learning for students and benefit local communities. Co-creation entails the full participation of students and their families throughout the discovery science missions, including joint brainstorming meetings, decisions about the implementations of the science missions, and their participation in international project meetings.

The Role of Families in the Process of Family-based Open Science Schooling

In Family-based Open Science Schooling, families have a significant role in the science learning process of students. Families help students to implement their selected discovery science missions in several consecutive steps alongside science teachers, local stakeholders and science resources:

Overview of the Realization of Science Discovery Missions

In Family-based Open Science Schooling, the realization of science discovery missions by students, their families, and teachers comprises the following components:

CHAPTER 2

STEPS TO A SUCCESSFUL FAMILY-
BASED OPEN SCIENCE SCHOOLING
IMPLEMENTATION

In the following chapters, we explain how to successfully implement Family-based Open Science Schooling in your school system.

**STEPS TO A SUCCESSFUL
FAMILY-BASED OPEN
SCIENCE SCHOOLING
IMPLEMENTATION**

IMPLEMENTING A PARTICIPATORY APPROACH

1 Participatory Approach

In this section we will learn:

- How to implement Family-based Open Science Schooling.*
- Why to implement Family-based Open Science Schooling.*
- How to involve families in the process.*
- How to establish a successful home-school collaboration.*
- The strategies that have worked best to motivate family members to be more involved in the missions with their children.*

How to Implement Family-based Open Science Schooling?

Fostering Participation

In line with the participatory design approach, Family-based Open Science Schooling entails the full participation of students and their families throughout the immersive science missions, including joint brainstorming meetings, decisions about the implementations of the immersive science missions, and their participation in the decision-making about their learning experience.

Click on the picture for more tips on successful participatory design!

Tips to carry out successful participatory design workshops with students, family members, and local community members

Set clear goals for your workshop

Create a vibrant atmosphere in which all participants feel comfortable to speak out their thoughts; engage every single participant

Ensure that all participants have an equal opportunity to meet, discuss, and understand the workshop goals

Trigger ideas by providing real-life examples

Encourage lively discussions and allow participants to think wildly; all ideas are valid!

Visualize the ideas and identify together the best way forward

Summarise the results of the workshop in an easy-to-understand language

Why to Implement Family-based Open Science Schooling?

Home-school collaboration and partnership have shown to boost learning motivation and to promote cultural and educational interactions.

Adding to this, innovative didactical approaches such as open science schooling that reveal the relevance of science learning in everyday life provide a source of motivation for learners. The aim is to get family members involved by supporting them to develop STEAM-rich environments at home.

Science disengagement often occurs in secondary school, when students are between 12 and 15 years of age, implying that science resistance is closely tied to the formation of a student's identity and personality. Research has shown that family involvement contributes to students' positive educational outcomes. Therefore, Family-based Open Science Schooling aims at:

- 1. Encouraging families to become real partners in school life and activities through the participatory design of the immersive science missions**
- 2. Co-creating "science everywhere" activities alongside teachers, students, and families to support responsible science education**
- 3. Supporting the deployment of immersive joint science missions involving the community as a whole so that schools become agents of community well-being**

By that, Family-based Open Science Schooling focuses on secondary schools, giving teachers, students, and families the chance and tools to construct diverse learning systems in order to engage young students in science!

How to Involve Families?

The active involvement of families is vital to the science learning process of students. Therefore, it is critical that family members and in particular parents feel invited and welcomed by their children and teachers to actively participate in the immersive science missions. As studies have shown, families find a way to be involved even in the case of the resource constrains if they feel that their participation is desired. To ensure that parents feel welcomed, different measures can be taken.

How to Establish a Successful Home-school Collaboration?

To achieve successful home-school collaborations, we have noticed that it is important to change the mindsets of all actors involved including teachers, students, their families and local stakeholders towards science learning, to build trustful, close relationships and accommodate new ways of interactions within the participatory approach of Family-based Open Science Schooling.

2

@Home Science Discovery
Missions

**IMPLEMENT
@HOME SCIENCE
DISCOVERY**

In this section we will learn:

- How implement @Home-science Discovery Missions.*
- Examples of Successfully Implemented @Home-science Discovery Missions.*
- Students' and Families' Feedback to the @Home-science Discovery Missions.*

Plan and implement **@home-science discovery missions:** students and their families are encouraged to explore exciting science challenges at home with the help of but not micromanaged by science teachers. To jointly elaborate a broader picture of the issue under study and propose potential solutions, students and their families might rely on interactions and collaboration with scientific sources in their local community such as research and innovation centers or NGOs.

Science mission is an interactive learning activity or experiment which consists of a set of steps designed to test a hypothesis. Missions are not punctual experiments and could last from few days to even months. Students and their families work in teams to learn through engaging, long-term missions in their diverse local communities.

Teachers could act as guides by suggesting but not advising specific issues that could be studied and ways to approach them. However, they do not micromanage the choice of the issue under study or the development and implementation of the science missions to allow for students' and their families' creativity and freedom. It is essential for students and their families to decide freely in which issue they are interested in and to allow for their growing problem-solving efficacy, creativity, and collaboration and communication skills as well as the greatest impact on the community.

Successfully Implemented @Home Science Discovery Missions

To help you implement Family-based Open Science Schooling as easily and effectively as possible AT HOME, here are some tested home-science discovery missions and feedback from both students and families. Click on the picture to see the explanations of each part.

The screenshot displays the user interface for an @Home Science Discovery Mission. At the top, there is an Erasmus+ logo and the text "@ HOME SCIENCE DISCOVERY MISSIONS - TITLE HERE". Below this, a yellow speech bubble contains the text "What Do We Need?". To the right, a green box is labeled "Protocol" and contains the number "1.". Below the protocol, there is a section titled "YOUR MISSION REPORT" with an orange background. To the right of the report, there is a "Did you know?" box with a lightbulb icon and a "Learn more!" button. Below these elements, there are two feedback sections: "Student feedback - How did you like this mission?" and "Family feedback - How did you like this mission?". Each feedback section includes a row of five smiley face icons (from sad to happy) and corresponding radio button options: "not at all", "not much", "a bit", "liked it", "liked it a lot", and "liked it best". Below the family feedback, there is a question "Did you use the 'Learn more!' resources?" with "Yes" and "No" radio button options. At the bottom, there is a text input field for "What was good/bad about this mission?".

@Home Science Discovery (Missions)

FAMILY-BASED OPEN SCIENCE SCHOOLING

@ HOME SCIENCE DISCOVERY MISSIONS – BIRDS' WATCHING

Materials

Protocol

Task report

Feedback
(student + guardian)

What Do We Need?

- Window, balcony overlooking the street or yard (you could also visit a local park, if safe)
- Binoculars (optional)
- Bird guide or internet access
- Notebook, pen/pencil

Protocol

1. Observe early in the morning or later in the evening, when many of the urban birds are most active.
2. Watch the environment and the habitat. Birds generally prefer vegetation areas with food and shelter.
3. Be patient. Stay (at the window) without making a noise and avoid quick movements
4. Use bird guides or websites to help identify species.
5. Pay attention to the size of the body, colours, and proportion of the length of the beak and feet.
6. Record the species observed and heard in a field notebook. It is important to note the date, time of observation, location, and behaviour.
7. Repeat the process for several days. Factors such as climate and human intrusion influence their behaviour.

YOUR MISSION REPORT

- How many kinds of birds did you observe? Describe them and their behaviours!
- How are these birds a part of your local ecosystem? (for example, their importance, interaction with people, etc.)
- Where do you see science in this mission?

Did you know?
Birds (and other animals!) used to deliver our mail before!

Learn more!

Video here:
<https://tinyurl.com/ycucjn1b>

Interesting fact

Further info

Country (Choose an item,) Grade (Choose an item,)

Student feedback - How did you like this mission?

not at all
 not much
 a bit
 liked it
 liked it a lot
 liked it best

Family feedback - How did you like this mission?

not at all
 not much
 a bit
 liked it
 liked it a lot
 liked it best

Did you use the 'Learn more!' resources? Yes No

What was good/bad about this mission?

The following @home-science discovery missions were suggested as examples to students and their families to explore exciting science experiments at home during the first round of the FBOSS project. The students and families were free to choose their own science missions.

HOME SCIENCE DISCOVERY MISSIONS – BIRDS' WATCHING

What Do We Need?

- Window, balcony overlooking the street or place you could also visit a local park, if safe
- Binoculars (optional)
- Field guide or internet access
- Notebook, pen/pencil

Protocol

- Observe early in the morning or later in the evening, when many of the birds look at most active.
- Watch the environment and the habitat. Birds generally prefer vegetation areas with food and shelter.
- Be patient. Stay at the window without making a noise and avoid quick movements.
- Use field guides or websites to help identify species.
- Pay attention to the size of the body, colour, and proportion of the length of the beak and feet.
- Record the species observed and heard in a field notebook. It is important to note the date, time of observation, location, and behaviour.
- Repeat the process for several days. Factors such as climate and human impact influence their behaviour.

YOUR MISSION REPORT

How many birds of birds did you observe? Describe them and their behaviour?

How are these birds a part of your local ecosystem? (for example, their importance, interactions with people, etc.)

Where do you see science in this mission?

Learn more!

Video here: <https://tinyurl.com/y9xqpb>

Did you know? Read/Write Aloud! You need to identify our word 'beak'!

Learn more!

Video here: <https://tinyurl.com/y9xqpb>

Source: Choose as item. **Link:** Choose as item.

Student feedback - How did you like this mission?

not at all | not much | a bit | liked it | liked it a lot

Family feedback - How did you like this mission?

not at all | not much | a bit | liked it | liked it a lot

Did you use the 'Learn more!' resources? Yes No

What was good/bad about this mission?

HOME SCIENCE DISCOVERY MISSIONS – CRYSTAL GROWING (sugar)

What Do We Need?

- Water
- Sugar (the one at home)
- Clear jar (glass preferably)
- Coffee filter
- String of yarn or thin wood stick
- Patience!

Protocol

- Put one cup of water to boil.
- Stir in the 3 cups of sugar slowly in the hot water until is saturated. Try stir one spoon of sugar at a time until the sugar does not dissolve in the water anymore. This means that the water is saturated.
- Let the mixture stand and cool.
- Trace the mixture into the jar using a coffee filter. Discard solid parts (undissolved sugar at the bottom of the boiled water).
- Insert a yarn string or thin wood stick to the middle of the jar hanging from the top. You can use a pencil to secure the yarn or a clip to hold the wood stick in place.
- Let it rest undisturbed. Observe the growth over several days.

YOUR MISSION REPORT

Measure your crystal after 7 days - how big is it?

What other materials found at home could you use to grow crystals? Report on your results!

How are crystals important in our planet?

Where do you see science in this mission?

Learn more!

Video here: <https://tinyurl.com/y9w365>

Did you know? Science crystals are used in the rock industry to manufacture things that power our computers.

Learn more!

Video here: <https://tinyurl.com/y9w365>

Source: Choose as item. **Link:** Choose as item.

Student feedback - How did you like this mission?

not at all | not much | a bit | liked it | liked it a lot

Family feedback - How did you like this mission?

not at all | not much | a bit | liked it | liked it a lot

Did you use the 'Learn more!' resources? Yes No

What was good/bad about this mission?

HOME SCIENCE DISCOVERY MISSIONS – PROTEIN GLUE

What Do We Need?

- Milk (skimmed low fat)
- Wool
- Baking soda (baking powder)
- Coffee filter

Protocol

- Put two mugs of milk into a kettle and heat to about 50 °C. Try not to let boil.
- Put the mixture stop by stop, stirring constantly until you see that two distinct layers form.
- Let the mixture stand and cool.
- Filter the mixture using a coffee filter, recovering only the solid parts.
- Dry out the mixture with absorbent paper and place it in a bowl.
- Add 3 teaspoons of baking soda and mix well until a homogeneous mixture similar to white glue appears.

YOUR MISSION REPORT

What happens when the temperature of the milk is too hot or the milk boils stop??

What type of materials can you glue with this mixture? Why? (for example plastic paper, cardboard, etc.)

For how long is the glue effective? Does it still work after 1 day? 1 week?

Where do you see science in this mission?

Learn more!

Video here: <https://tinyurl.com/yd7fz7>

Did you know? Protein glue is used in the rock industry to manufacture things that power our computers.

Learn more!

Video here: <https://tinyurl.com/yd7fz7>

Source: Choose as item. **Link:** Choose as item.

Student feedback - How did you like this mission?

not at all | not much | a bit | liked it | liked it a lot

Family feedback - How did you like this mission?

not at all | not much | a bit | liked it | liked it a lot

Did you use the 'Learn more!' resources? Yes No

What was good/bad about this mission?

HOME SCIENCE DISCOVERY MISSIONS – NATURAL pH INDICATOR

What Do We Need?

- Red cabbage
- A small pot or pan
- Water
- Cover glass tops

Protocol

- Cut 2-3 pieces of red cabbage into small pieces and put it in a pot.
- Cover the pot with water and cook for 10 minutes at medium heat. (NOTE: you can also use a blender to chop the pieces with the cut from the red cabbage.)
- Allow the mixture to cool and strain the colour of the liquid (retained).
- Put a small amount of the liquid into three different glasses.
- Use a pipette to add the liquid to water. (If the mixture already has a colour, use another water sample.)
- Use a pipette to add a drop of vinegar and stir with a spoon. Observe the colour. Add more vinegar until the colour stops test change completely. (If the solution needs to be red, it means to add the small amount of blue water.)
- Repeat and stir with a spoon. What happens to the colour of the liquid?

YOUR MISSION REPORT

Observe what the liquid colour changes following your 'Make a chart of colours' table and try to explain the change in colour.

How can you use this problem solver? (If, otherwise, why not?) How do you use the problem solver?

Where do you see science in this mission?

Learn more!

Video here: <https://tinyurl.com/y9xqpb>

Did you know? Read/Write Aloud! You need to identify our word 'pH' of the acid (the juice).

Learn more!

Video here: <https://tinyurl.com/y9xqpb>

Source: Choose as item. **Link:** Choose as item.

Student feedback - How did you like this mission?

not at all | not much | a bit | liked it | liked it a lot

Family feedback - How did you like this mission?

not at all | not much | a bit | liked it | liked it a lot

Did you use the 'Learn more!' resources? Yes No

What was good/bad about this mission?

HOME SCIENCE DISCOVERY MISSIONS – RUBIK'S CUBE MACHINE (savage/effect)

What Do We Need?

- Your imagination! (After you can get inspiration from online resources).
- Choose a task that your "machine" would accomplish.
- Collect necessary materials from things available at home.

Protocol

- Collect your materials (e.g., old box, dominos, marbles, anything available).
- Start experimenting with simple tasks using the materials - be creative!
- Clarify your plan: remember the task your machine will accomplish: think in the chain of events that could lead your machine accomplish its task.
- Test it and deploy it!

YOUR MISSION REPORT

How are you identify cause/effect in nature?

How is this important in your life?

Where do you see science in this mission?

Learn more!

Video here: <https://tinyurl.com/y9xqpb>

Did you know? "Give the flag of a flag" usually it's a flag in French - set off a storm in French."

Learn more!

Video here: <https://tinyurl.com/y9xqpb>

Source: Choose as item. **Link:** Choose as item.

Student feedback - How did you like this mission?

not at all | not much | a bit | liked it | liked it a lot

Family feedback - How did you like this mission?

not at all | not much | a bit | liked it | liked it a lot

Did you use the 'Learn more!' resources? Yes No

What was good/bad about this mission?

The students and their families in Bulgaria tried out and reported various new and exciting @home science discovery missions.

Family in Bulgaria

Birds Watching

What Do We Need?

- Window, balcony overlooking the street or yard (you could also visit a local park, if safe)
- Binoculars (optional)
- Bird guide or internet access
- Notebook, pen/pencil

Protocol

1. Observe early in the morning or later in the evening, when many of the urban birds are most active.
2. Watch the environment and the habitat. Birds generally prefer vegetation areas with food and shelter.
3. Be patient. Stay (at the window) without making a noise and avoid quick movements
4. Use bird guides or websites to help identify species.
5. Pay attention to the size of the body, colours, and proportion of the length of the beak and feet.
6. Record the species observed and heard in a field notebook. It is important to note the date, time of observation, location, and behaviour.
7. Repeat the process for several days. Factors such as climate and human intrusion influence their behaviour.

Elephant Toothpaste

What Do We Need?

- 50 ml hydrogen peroxide 30%
- Potassium permanganate (2g)
- 10 ml H₂O
- 2 ml. of liquid dish soap
- Food colouring (optional)

Protocol

1. Dissolve potassium permanganate in water.
2. Pour 50 ml. of hydrogen peroxide in a glass bottle
3. Put 2 ml. of liquid dish soap
4. Then put food colouring for better effect.
5. Carefully and quickly mix the potassium permanganate in the liquid of hydrogen peroxide
6. Step aside and watch.

Family in Bulgaria

The students and their families in Lithuania and Greece also tried out and reported various new and exciting @home science discovery missions.

Family in Lithuania

HOMEMADE LAVENDER OIL

What Do We Need?

- 100 grams of lavender
- Some water
- A refractory saucepan
- A bowl
- Ice cubes
- A glass bottle

Protocol

1. Clean the lavender
2. Put the bowl into the centre inside the saucepan
3. Distribute the lavender around the bowl
4. Add some water on the lavender
5. Let it boil
6. Put the ice cube on the lid of the saucepan
7. Lower the temperature and let the lavender boil, adding continuously ice cubs
8. Remove it from the hot plate (or any kind of electrical device you use)
9. Pour the condensed lavender oil from the bowl in glass bottle and let it cool
10. Your homemade essential lavender oil is ready to be used!

Family in Greece

Dancing Paper

What Do We Need?

- A balloon
- Very small pieces of paper
- Woollen fabric or human hair

Protocol

1. Cut some small pieces of paper (the smaller the better) and leave them on a table.
2. Inflate the balloon.
3. Rub the balloon on the woollen fabric or your hair quickly.
4. Get the balloon close to the pieces of paper slowly.
5. What are the papers doing???

The students and their families in Turkey also shared their exciting @home science discovery missions.

Family in Turkey

Natural pH

What Do We Need?

- Red cabbage
- Water
- A small pot or pan
- A strainer
- 3 clear glass cups

Protocol

1. Cut 2-3 leaves of red cabbage into small pieces and put in a pan/pot.
2. Cover the leaves with water and cook for 40 minutes at medium heat. (NOTE: you can also use a blender to make juice with the cut leaves and water without cooking it!)
3. Allow the mixture to cool and strain (the colour of the liquid is dark purple).
4. Pour a small amount of the liquid into three different glasses.
5. In glass 1, add to the liquid tap water. (TIP: the solution should be a clearer purple/blueish colour).
6. In glass 2, add to the liquid a drop of vinegar and stir with a spoon. Observe the colour. Add more vinegar until the colour does not change anymore. (TIP: the solution should be red)
7. In glass 3, add to the liquid a drop of glass cleaner (ammonia) and stir with a spoon. What happens to the solution? Why?

Family in Turkey

Homemade Yogurt

What Do We Need?

- A bottle of raw milk (cow, sheep, goat; depends on your likings)
- Stove
- Yoghurt (bought from the store)
- Blanket or rug
- Jars

Protocol

1. Pour the raw milk in a pot.
2. Put the pot on the stove. Milk has to go through thermal treatment as it contains dangerous for the body bacteria.
3. After brewing it, divide the milk in the jars.
4. Take about a half of a teaspoon of yoghurt and put this portion in each one of your jars.
5. Stir well. Lactobacillus bulgaricus, the bacteria causing milk fermentation, transfers from the yoghurt into the hot milk.
6. Seal the jars and wrap them tightly in a blanket or a rug. In order for the fermentation to happen, the milk has to maintain constant temperature of about 45°C.
7. After 3-4 hours the process is done. Unwrapping the jars, you can see that the milk has changed its physical state!

Check YouTube channel of Family-based Open Science Schooling project and watch more videos! (Click on the photo)

Students' and Families' Feedback to the @Home Science Discovery Missions

The feedback from students and their families was very positive. They liked in particular that the @home-science discovery missions allowed them to follow their interests, to use their creativity and gain experiences, to bond with their family, and get a better understanding of science and their learning process.

3

Science Discovery Missions with the Community

In this section we will learn:

IMPLEMENT SCIENCE DISCOVERY MISSIONS WITH THE COMMUNITY

- How to implement science discovery missions with the community – step by step guide*
- Examples of successfully implemented science discovery missions with the community*
 - Bulgaria
 - Greece
 - Lithuania
 - Poland
 - Turkey

Plan and implement science discovery missions with the community: in contrast to @home-science missions, science discovery missions with the community encourage students and their families to tackle issues with which their local communities are confronted such as vandalized children's playgrounds or low corona vaccination awareness. Such science discovery missions with the community include considerable collaboration with local science resources such as

- Private companies with science-related activity, citizens' organisations working with science-related challenges in the community, such as science in society
- Public authorities with an interest in science learning and science in the community
- Various forms of science educations and research bodies, private or public
- Open science centres in the community or region
- Entrepreneurial hubs engaged in science in various ways

As in the case of @home-science missions, science discovery missions with the community require you to act as guides by suggesting potential community issues and ways to approach those.

Steps To Creating Science Discovery Missions With The Community

Practical Examples Of Science Discovery Missions With The Community

3

Science Discovery Missions
with the Community

BULGARIA

Gimnaziya S Prepodavane
Na Chuzhdi Ezici
"Romen Rolan"
School

Practical Examples Of Science Discovery Missions With The Community - Bulgaria

Community Mission 1:

The students were interested in improving the conditions of the playgrounds in their town. Under the guidance and with the help of their teachers and families, they created an [interactive map](#) of children's playgrounds in order to provide families with an overview over the individual playgrounds and their condition in their community. Finally, they shared the created interactive maps with the Young Mayor of Stara Zagora and the city council representatives for future improvements.

Practical Examples Of Science Discovery Missions With The Community - Bulgaria

Community Mission 2:

To raise awareness of the importance of vitamin D for a strong immune system and the monitoring of blood sugar levels, the students chose two topics to work on in the second round of community missions. With the help of both parents and teachers, they researched the causes, symptoms, prevention, and treatment of lacking vitamin D and too low/high blood sugar levels. To provide information to their community, they created available online resources summarizing their research findings such as:

- Posters to illustrate facts about the topic
- Online games to be played in English on the topic of health ([Vitamin D - Jeopardy Game](#))
- A quiz posted on the school's social media channels that tests a person's general knowledge on the topic
- A lesson plan developed by the teachers to be used as a teaching resource on the topic of health education

3

Science Discovery Missions
with the Community

GREECE

**Platon M.E.P.E
School**

3

Practical Examples Of Science Discovery Missions With The Community - Greece

Community Mission 1:

For their first discovery mission with the community, the students decided that they wanted to work on a mission that had to do with the environment. They did some research about the garbage in Greece and more specific in their living region. They had a discussion with the person responsible from the municipality and talked with him about the problems that they had discovered. To raise awareness regarding the problem, the students decided to do a symbolic move and gather garbage from a park near their school with the help of school staff and families.

Practical Examples Of Science Discovery Missions With The Community - Greece

Community Mission 2:

For their second discovery mission with the community, the students decided to continue working with the environmental issues and therefore, they got deeper. The First team worked on the “Water footprint” and the second team worked on “Food waste”. They did some research on these two subjects. To raise awareness, they presented their findings to the students and teachers at their school. They created a quiz and power point presentation and asked the students and teachers to discuss the issue with their families and friends.

Facts and figures about food waste

All the world’s nearly one billion hungry people could be fed on less than a quarter of the food that is wasted in the US, UK and Europe.

<https://www.fix.com/assets/content/15725/whos-wasting-the-most-food.png>

WHO'S WASTING THE MOST FOOD?
ANYWHERE FOOD IS GROWN, SOLD, OR EATEN, FOOD IS WASTED. HOWEVER CONSUMERS ARE DEFINITELY THE BIGGEST SOURCE OF FOOD WASTE

Residential	44%
Restaurants	33%
Grocery Stores	11%
Institutional	10%
Industrial	2%

Water footprint does not only apply on the food we consume, but also on the clothes we wear, the items we use; It is calculated in every subject such as housing, transportation, entertainment, education, business life. It is an account that shows the development level of countries, measures the tendency of institutions to environmental issues, and shows how conscious individuals are about water use.

https://live.staticflickr.com/81108/8558534231_1a46b24b6d.jpg

3

Science Discovery Missions
with the Community

LITHUANIA

Pasvalio Levens
pagrindine mokykla
School

Practical Examples Of Science Discovery Missions With The Community - Lithuania

Community Mission 1:

To educate people about the importance of vaccination against COVID-19, the students designed educating activities that focused on the current health issues caused by COVID-19 worldwide. After doing research, they were sure that the vaccination against COVID-19 saves lives and is the fastest way to go back to the previous way of life without everyday life restrictions. During the mission alongside their families, they gained valuable knowledge and experiences, educated others about the benefits of the COVID-19 vaccination, and created posters and a video clip to share their gained knowledge.

Practical Examples Of Science Discovery Missions With The Community - Lithuania

Community Mission 2:

For their second community mission, the students and their families wanted to tackle environmental problems humankind is currently facing. They noticed that textile could take more than 200 years to decompose in landfills. People usually throw away their clothes and shoes. Therefore, oceans, rivers, and many other places are filled with old clothing items. To help the environment, the students raised awareness on upcycling and recycling of clothes. First, they created questionnaires to measure people's understanding of the problems of textile pollution. Then, together with their families, they created presentations, videos, a [Kahoot game](#), and workshops to educate people.

Practical Examples Of Science Discovery Missions With The Community - Lithuania

Community Mission 3:

In light of the unexpected war in Ukraine, the students and families started a new mission called "Helping Hands" and joined the volunteer organization "Stiprus Kartu (Strong Together)" to support Ukrainian citizens affected by the war. They raised money for donations, joined support events in the city, sent humanitarian help to Ukraine, and hosted Ukrainian refugees. Their textile recycling mission turned into donating clothes to those in need. Also, during the "St. Kazimieras" fair, families, students, and schoolteachers sold home-made food, bakery, arts and crafts through which they could collect and donate 603,76 euros to official funds in support of Ukraine. EVERY LITTLE MATTERS! In addition, to support the Ukrainians' freedom and peace, the school organized solidarity and unity action called "Ribbons of Support and Birds of Peace" during which families, students, and teachers decorated bridges with ribbons in the color of the Ukrainian flag.

3

Science Discovery Missions
with the Community

POLAND

Szkola Podstawowa nr 2 z
Oddziałami
Dwujęzycznymi im ks
Stanisława Konarskiego
School

Practical Examples Of Science Discovery Missions With The Community - Poland

Community Mission 1:

After joint meetings with families and teachers and brainstorming, the students got interested in increasing their community's awareness on environmental problems. They decided to show people how to help animals in to survive throughout winter and in breeding season in their community. They built winter boxes for butterflies, nesting boxes, and feeders for birds. Then they distributed the boxes in local parks, local estates, local kindergarten, and streets (with the agreement of their local municipality).

Building nests and placing them on trees plus some hugs and care for the birds.

Practical Examples Of Science Discovery Missions With The Community - Poland

Community Mission 2:

For their second community mission, the students wanted to learn more about medical first aid. Having in mind that the skill could save lives, the students learnt about CPR and how to help an unconscious person. After acquiring the knowledge, they demonstrated what they learnt to family members and other younger students, taught them about human biology and how it works and created an attitude of empathy and care for others. They also created posters to boost awareness.

TURKEY

Elazig Doga Anadolu
Lisesi
(Elazig Egitimcilik
Tic.ve San. A.S)
School

Practical Examples Of Science Discovery Missions With The Community - Turkey

Community Mission 1:

In order to raise awareness on existing professional careers, students, their families, and teachers organized a career day. Various business partners came together to share their knowledge about their jobs, educational backgrounds, and their skills. The activity not only gave the students an opportunity to get familiar with different career paths but also motivated and inspired them. The question-and-answer session was informative and lively and gave students a new idea. Based on the discussions on medical career paths, the group decided to create a brochure about the ways to protect the joints during winter. The brochure was shared with all the students of the school and their families.

Practical Examples Of Science Discovery Missions With The Community - Turkey

Community Mission 2:

In their second mission, students decided to increase kindness towards animals. They found out that some teachers and families are no longer able to take care of their pets and are therefore looking for new homes for them. The students shared the photos of the animals in the school's social media channels and searched for new homes for the pets. As part of this mission, they raised not only awareness on the living conditions of animals in the neighborhood, but also informed their community of shelters and their visiting hours and organized a small shelter at school.

CHAPTER 3

EVALUATION

Families' Evaluation – Initial Interview

To understand how families' understanding of science and the project may or may not change over time, it is best to conduct a pre-survey at the beginning of the project and a post-survey when it is in the last phase or when it is finished. In our Family-based project, we asked students to interview their families. Here are four questions we asked at the beginning to know how families perceived science in general and what expectations they had.

INITIAL INTERVIEW

- What does science mean to you?
- When you think about science, what images come to your mind?
- In your view, what does it mean to be a scientist?
- What do you expect from your participation in this project?

Families' most mentioned expectations of being involved in the Family-based Open Science Schooling project were being able to learn together with their children, spending more time together and broadening worldview both for themselves and their children. They also wished that they could be encouraging for their children during the project and hoped that their children would be more interested in science and choose a career in science in the future. For more study results, check [Family-based Open Science Schooling Research study](#) in our website.

Families' Evaluation – Final Interview

For the final interview, we prepared a more detailed interview questionnaire to gain deeper understanding of families' journey through our Family-based Open Science Schooling project. Families were interviewed by the teachers in this round.

FINAL INTERVIEW

Theme I - How is your child doing?

- What do you think about your child's participation in the project? Why is his/her participation important?
- What does your child speak to you about the project?
- What are the feelings of your child?
- Do you think your child is more interested in science than before?

Theme II - Parents' feelings towards the project

- How are your feelings towards the implementation of the Family-based OSS project?
- Has this project fostered better communication between you and the school? how? why?
- What can be different? What challenges have you faced? How can they be solved? What can be improved?
- To what extent do you think it is important to involve families in the process of science learning of their children? Why?
- Did you use to have hands-on science activities with your child at home before this project? What type of activities? In what circumstances?
- Do you feel it's easy to develop science activities with your child at home? Why?

Theme III - Parent-child relationship within Family-based OSS

- In your opinion, what has this project brought to your child? (e.g., new learning opportunities? new views of science? new international opportunities?, etc.) please elaborate.
- What has this project brought to your relationship with your child? (e.g., has the project impacted your relationship in any way? how?)
- Do you feel you have time to conciliate your daily responsibilities with your participation in this project?
- Have you been able to support your child as much as you expected? Why?

The following key findings extracted from the participating families' answers indicate that the Family-based Open Science Schooling helped families to have a more advanced and in-depth understanding of science in general as well as their children's science learning. For more study results, check [Family-based Open Science Schooling Research study](#) in our website.

Students' Evaluation – Pre/Post Test

To have a thorough evaluation of students' understanding of science and the project, it is recommended to conduct a pre-test and post-test survey for the students. Here is the tested qualitative/ quantitative survey of Family-based Open Science Schooling.

Pre/Post Test

- What does science mean to you?
- What does it mean to be a scientist?
- Have you participated in any kind of activity associated with science or scientific experiments outside OSS? If Yes, in what contexts? If No, why?
- Do you believe that science can be useful in your daily life? If Yes, in what way? If No, why?
- What do you think your parents expect from your science learning experience through this project? If Other, what expectations do you think your parents have?
 - I think they expect me to become a better science student
 - I think they expect me to become a better critical thinker
 - I think they expect me to have a career in science
 - I think my parent have no expectations
 - Other - If Other, what expectations do you think your parents have?
- What do YOU expect from your parents' involvement in your science learning experience through this project?
 - I expect them to be more involved in my school life
 - I expect them to understand better my future goals
 - I expect them to have a more positive attitude towards science
 - I expect them to be more interested in my science learning progress
 - Other - If Other, what expectations do you have
- Do you believe that your parents can establish a strong relationship with your school through this project? If Yes, how? If No, why?
- Do you believe that your parents will be more interested in your science learning activities through this project? If yes, how? If no, why?

Pre/Post Test

Select the picture (and mark one of the corresponding number) that best describes...

- the current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of what a science professional is 1 ○ 2 ○ 3 ○ 4 ○ 5 ○ 6 ○ 7 ○
- the extent to which your knowledge of science concepts matches that of a science professional 1 ○ 2 ○ 3 ○ 4 ○ 5 ○ 6 ○ 7 ○
- the extent to which your capacity to use science skills in a public setting matches that of a science professional 1 ○ 2 ○ 3 ○ 4 ○ 5 ○ 6 ○ 7 ○
- the extent to which your family thinks of you as a science professional 1 ○ 2 ○ 3 ○ 4 ○ 5 ○ 6 ○ 7 ○
- the extent to which you think your friends think of you as a science professional 1 ○ 2 ○ 3 ○ 4 ○ 5 ○ 6 ○ 7 ○
- the extent to which you think your teachers/instructors think of you as a science professional 1 ○ 2 ○ 3 ○ 4 ○ 5 ○ 6 ○ 7 ○

The results from the pre-test and post test shows that students' perception of the usefulness of science has improved. Four percent of the participating students thought science is not useful for everyone in the pre-test. In comparison, 100% of the participating students answered that science is useful in our daily lives in the post test. For more study results, check [Family-based Open Science Schooling Research study](#) in our website.

Do you believe that science can be useful in your daily life?

PRE-TEST

“Because in a pretty normal life with a pretty normal routine, I think science is just not useful”

“Science is useful in daily life but not for everyone.”

“Science is our everyday life!. Our feelings, air we breath, water we drink and food we eat, human birth, everything is Science!”

“Science is hidden inside almost every daily thing, for example our phones created from people who know science and technology and much more.”

POST TEST

“Science can be used to solve global problems or to reduce the chance of the occurrence of a disaster.”

“It's all around us. The science is all of the world.”

“In various aspects even now doing this survey, I am using technologies and electricity. When I turn around myself most of the things are connected with science.”

Families' and Students' Perspectives on What Science Means to Them

What Does Science Mean To You?

“A room full of books on various topics, and from each book extract a lot of new information. I imagine a sphere that resembles planet Earth. I imagine a huge research center full of scientists performing various experiments in laboratories. An adult with a small child hand in hand. The more the adult responds, the more curious the child becomes.”

“Science is everything that has to do with technology.”

“Science is understanding of world. Science is questioning, attracting, finding new solutions for problems, so it is a way which provides better understanding life.”

“In my opinion, science is discovering something new, unknown, some intellectual adventure. When I think about science, my thoughts go to foreign languages, medicine, the Internet. In my opinion, scientists are positively crazy madmen whom I admire and respect.”

“Since one of my future goals is to follow the route of science and become a scientist myself, I find science very important.”

“Science means a lot, because it can help me learn more about the earth.”

“Science represents not only humanity's will to strive for progress, but also its aim to explain how everything in the world works.”

“Science is everything around us, the trees, the plants, the animals, humans and the relationship between them”

“people probably can't imagine life without electricity, transport, internet, knowledge. All those things are based on science. Advances in technology and science are transforming our world at an incredible pace, our children's future will surely be filled with leaps in technology we can only imagine”

Teachers' Evaluation – Questionnaire

To be able to improve Family-based Open Science Schooling and gain new ideas how to increase involvement of families, it is recommended to conduct a survey with schoolteachers towards the end of the project or after the project is finished. Here is the questionnaire conducted with participating teachers of our project.

TEACHER'S QUESTIONNAIRE

Positive and Challenging

- Think about the Family-based Project, what have you liked the most so far?
- What challenges have you faced during the first phase of the project? Name at least 3
- In what way COVID-19 interfered with the dynamic of the project team locally?
- In what way COVID-19 interfered with the relationship between you and the students during the project?
- In what way COVID-19 interfered with the relationship between you and the students' parents during the project?
- Describe the strategies that you have used to overcome the above-mentioned interferences.

Communication

- What communication channels have worked best for you to involve students in developing their missions?
WhatsApp / Emails / Face to face meetings / Phone call meetings / MS Teams meetings / Zoom meetings / Other
- What Communication channels have worked best for you to involve students' parents/family members in developing the students' missions?
WhatsApp / Emails / Face to face meetings / Phone call meetings / MS Teams meetings / Zoom meetings / Other
- What challenges in concern with communication channels with the students have you observed so far?
- What challenges in concern with communication channels with the families have you observed so far?
- Please describe the strategies that you have deployed to tackle the challenges concerning communication channels.
- Please describe the strategies that have worked best to motivate family members to be more involved in the missions with their children.
- Please describe the strategies that have failed to motivate family members to be more involved in the missions with their children.

Support and Bias (transforming organizations | build relationships | changing mindsets)

- In your view, how can the families support science learning of their children?
- In your view, how can teachers support science learning of the families?
- In your view, what negative bias in attitude towards science learning already exists among families?
- In your view, how can teachers help with reducing or eliminating existing negative bias attitudes towards science learning?
- In your view, how can teachers and families collaborate best?
- In your view, what is meant by home and family culture?
- In your view, how students' home and family culture is affecting students' interest in science learning?
- In your view, what is the added value of involving family members in the students' science education?
- In your views, what changes at the institution/organization level should take place to support family involvement in students' science education?
- Have these changes occurred at your organization? Y/N Please justify.
- What kind of support have you received from your organization (school administration) to develop and implement the Family-based OSS methodology locally? Please describe.

5= completely effective 1= not effective at all	5	4	3	2	1		
In your opinion, how effective do you find parents' involvement in students' science learning using Family-based OSS?							
In your opinion, how effective do you find parents' involvement in students' science learning using traditional methods?							
In your opinion, how effective do you find students' involvement in science learning using Family-based OSS?							
In your opinion, how effective do you find students' involvement in science learning using traditional methods?							
In your opinion, how effective do you find to involve community stakeholders in students' science learning using Family-based OSS?							
In your opinion, how effective do you find to involve community stakeholders in students' science learning using traditional methods?							
5= very easy 1= not easy at all							
How easy was it to involve parents in the at home science missions through the Family-based OSS methodology?							
How easy was it to involve parents in the science missions in the community through the Family-based OSS methodology?							
How easy was the process of reaching out and involving community partners through Family-based OSS methodology?							
How easy was it to obtain support from your organisation to implement the Family-based OSS methodology?							
5= very well 1= not well at all							
How well do you consider students have learned science concepts through Family-based OSS compared to traditional methods?							
How well do you consider Family-based OSS methodology has met students' needs compared to traditional methods?							
5= very motivated 1= not at all motivated							
In your opinion, how motivated were the students to learn and practice science with their family members through Family-based OSS compared to traditional methods?							
In your opinion, how motivated were the parents to learn and practice science with their children through Family-based OSS compared to traditional methods?							
In your opinion, how motivated were the community stakeholders to be involved through Family-based OSS in students' science learning compared to traditional methods?							
How motivated were you (the teacher) to involve family members through Family-based OSS in students' science learning compared to traditional methods?							
How motivated were you (the teacher) to involve community stakeholders through Family-based OSS in students' science learning compared to traditional methods?							

Participating teachers' answers to the questionnaire indicates that teachers find Family-based Open Science Schooling method more effective to involve students, parents and community in science learning compared to traditional methods. For more study results, check [Family-based Open Science Schooling Research study](#) in our website.

Effectiveness Of Students' Involvement In Science Learning

USING TRADITIONAL METHODS (%)

USING FAMILY-BASED OPEN SCIENCE SCHOOLING (%)

Effectiveness Of Parents' Involvement In Students' Science Learning

Effectiveness To Involve Community Stakeholders In Students' Science Learning

CHAPTER 4

GENERAL PERSPECTIVES

In this chapter, you can find students' reflective perspective of their Family-based Open Science Schooling journey as well as some general tips for families and teachers to get their Family-based Open Science Schooling project off the ground to a good start.

1st important outcome

GET DEEPER INTO SCIENCE

Template provided by the coordinator → Template created by our students

2nd important outcome

We created awareness in our homes and in our community about these 2 important subjects!

What is food waste?

What is water footprint?

Student Teams' Graphical Representation Of Their Family-based Open Science Schooling Journey - Greece

POLAND

HOLOGRAM

Life Cycle of a Monarch Butterfly

Labels in the life cycle diagram: Egg, Caterpillar, Pupa, Adult.

Labels in the butterfly diagram: cephalum, ocellus, glasscaea wargony, zwiazka szkieletowa, body, skrzydła przednie, skrzydła tyłne, odwłok, anteny, głowa, tułów, nogi.

Student Teams' Graphical Representation Of Their Family-based Open Science Schooling Journey - Poland

Students' Perspective Regarding Working Online vs F2F

During the face-to-face part of our project's Mobility event in 2022, participating students illustrated their family-based Open Science Schooling journey regarding their Online and F2F experiences. All of them described their online experience as quiet, sitting alone in front of their computers, and not much fun. Whereas for the F2F part, they described their experience as being more exciting, collaborative and motivational since they could share ideas easily and get to know each other better. One student said, *"online was like being in the dark but face-to-face was like a gold for me."*

General Tips For Families And Teachers

TIPS FOR FAMILIES

Be open to change

Show your excitement and enthusiasm to implement science missions at home

Be active and together with your child/children search for new ideas as science missions

Allow and encourage trial and error approach

Ask for clear instructions and help when needed

Encourage active learning and problem solving

Be aware that your involvement even the tiniest one matters to your child/children

Act as a supporter and an explorer

TIPS FOR TEACHERS

Network and involve professionals

Involve families as early as possible and in all stages

Listen to families needs and act accordingly (e.g., some families might prefer group family mission to individual ones)

Allow and encourage trial and error approach

Value even the small effort from families and give credits to them

Take time to explain the procedure and scaffold throughout the process

Bear in mind that not all families are motivated, and some might be skeptical

Act as a knowledge facilitator not a knowledge carrier

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSIONS

The feedback of students, their families, and teachers to the Erasmus+ Family-based Open Science Schooling Project highlights the significant and appreciated role that family members and especially parents can play in students' science learning process. It also underlines the contribution that real-life experimentations can make to students' learning process, local community issues, and family bonds.

We therefore recommend engaging young students in science learning by simulating learning through discovering in an intricate relation between home, school, local stakeholders, and science resources and through activities promoting their curiosity, open-mindedness, resilience, and problem-solving attitudes.

Working online vs F2F – Students' Drawing (Mobility 2022)

Spreading the Seed of Knowledge – Students' Drawing (Mobility 2022)

It is essential to establish science as a positive value in students' identity by creating science learning environments at school and at home that allow for students' co-creation of knowledge based on their individual interests and aspirations for the future.

It is also fundamental to involve family members in students' science learning processes and strengthen home-school collaboration. It can be done by giving students science subjects to work on at home and through hands on scientific experiences at home and at school that encourage students to question and study scientific phenomena.

Family-based Open Science Schooling promotes community involvement and supports different forms of scientific co-creation activities while removing boundaries between civil society and science and between scientists and schools. This methodology represents one opportunity to revamp students' learning experiences, local community and family bonds and its implementation should be therefore promoted at the European and international scale.

Family-based Open Science Schooling

Capacity and Guidance Building in Secondary Schools for Involving Young Students' Families in Open Science Schooling Activities to Foster Responsible Science Education

Knowledge and Quality Assurance Partners

Practice Partners (Schools)

